

Research Article

ANGLICISMS AND THEIR USE BY ALBANIAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS			Education
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Abstract			
<p>English language as an international language is used as a Lingua Franca in a global level. Albanian and English language belong to two different language families and they are therefore quite different in different linguistic levels. Despite of this, many words with English origin were borrowed into Albanian language and most of them are accommodated in a way that they are not considered anymore as words with foreign origin. Nowadays, as we live in the era of technology and Internet, the spread of English words is common, especially among young students. They use them as part of their communication between them, but not only. They encounter English words in their school books, and they hear English words at school, especially when talking to their friends. The problem of language change has the root in the inappropriate and uncontrolled use of the language by all Albanian speakers, especially by journalists, publishers and editors, who through their work have the ability to easily spread new words.</p>			

Introduction

Albanian language is a very rich language in lexical and phraseological terms. However, even in the earliest lexicographical works of the Albanian language, there are noticed words with different origins. Recently, almost all of languages of the world, more or less, are influenced by English language.

Words with English origin, that have become part of the lexicon of various languages, are known as *anglicisms*. In Albanian language, anglicisms are found in different writings, articles, books, televisions, various communication environments, and they are even used by the highest structures of the state and prominent intellectuals. The use of English words is sometimes seen as a necessity, primarily due to the fact that many of them are used to name concepts that have entered into Albanian language along with relevant words, such as the words: *computer, scanner, printer, dollar, poster, etc.*

English influence on Albanian language

According to Jani Thomai, the Albanian language is open to anglicisms when they carry a new meaning, a new nuance in meaning or a new stylistic nuance, especially in the field of informatics, finance, market, economy, business, modern arts, etc. In the above cases, borrowings from English language have enriching values, but if they are borrowed without any control or

obstruction, then they turn into harmful phenomena for the fight and prevention of which must be made greatest efforts⁴.

According to Xhevat Lloshi, the arrival of anglicisms in the Albanian language is not seen as the arrival of other borrowings that have entered in different historical periods. According to him, we are facing an intervention of English borrowings in Albanian language that do not come just to meet the shortcomings and needs of Albanian, they are not even transitory and is not expected to change anything in the future because the wave of globalization is also global.⁵

As the language of globalization and technology, English language has expanded and is now used not only in particular discourses of human activity, but it has already become part of people's daily lives.

It is a fact that the period of time in which we live is known as the age of technology and the Internet. Based on this, the use of anglicisms is seen as a less troubling phenomenon compared to the use of foreign words with English origin. Such words are circulating and are used by almost all generations, especially by young people, and moreover, their meanings are understandable. For example, "*Daunlodova një fajll nga plejstori*" is a very common sentence, even though if we analyze it, only the numeral *një* (*one*) and the preposition *nga* (*from*) are Albanian words, whereas the nouns *fajll* (*file*) and *plejstori* (*playstore*), as well as the verb *daunlodova* (*downloaded*) are all English words. They are used by Albanians and are constantly expanding the limits of their use.

According to Vesel Nuhiu, journalists, official speakers, public workers, intellectuals, professors, academics who in most of the cases consciously do not respect the standard language norm have an important role in distorting the Albanian language in general. On the other hand, the other group that influences the distortion of the Albanian language and which is larger than the first group consists of singers, workers of culture and art, young journalists, sellers, etc. For this reason, he says that Albanian language needs changes, but reasonable and judged changes. Institutions that should take measures against these deviations and normative violations of the language have become anemic, primarily due to the great shortage of financial resources, but also due to the very dense deviations that are made, and therefore their power to undertake effective measures so far have shown weak results.⁶

Media plays an important role in the spread of various phenomena, including the spread of anglicisms and foreign words. According to Hajri Shehu, journalists and show hosts have the text and the context in their hands. They have a duty and responsibility, just like lexicographers, to take care of the lexicon, especially to avoid unnecessary foreign words or words that sound

⁴ Thomai, J. (2011). *Leksikologjia e gjuhës shqipe*, TOENA, Tiranë, p.262. (cited: *Fjala shqipe në vend të fjalës së huaj* (Fjalor I), 1998).

⁵ Lloshi, Xh. (2009). *Ndërrhyrja e huazimeve nga anglishtja*. IIIrd International Seminar of Albanology – State University of Tetova, pp.31-32.

⁶ Nuhiu, V. (2008). *Shqipja dhe huazimet angleze sot*. Thesis. nr. 1, Prishtina - Kosova, pp.112-114.

foreign.⁷ Journalists and editors should keep in mind that in front of them there are listeners and readers with different language competencies, and the inappropriate use of English words and phrases makes it difficult to convey the complete message to people with low language competence. On the other hand, it is necessary to consider young readers and listeners who easily absorb everything that is served to them.

English Words Used by Elementary School Students (Case Study)

No matter who is to blame for the language changes that occur as a result of using anglicisms and foreign English words, there are evident consequences. Changes are reflected in newspapers, magazines and even in school books and other educational school materials used by students. Some of the foreign words are used very often that Albanian students consider them to be Albanian words.

To provide evidence for the above claim we conducted a questionnaire. The questionnaire was responded by 40 students of the 9th grade, students at the elementary school “Rexhë Rushit Zajazi” in Zajas, North Macedonia. The questionnaire was realized using the online platform *Google Forms* that helped us receive immediate responses and an accurate percentage for their responses. The aim of the questionnaire was to reveal which anglicisms and foreign English words are used more frequently by them, the circumstances when they use them and the degree of understanding anglicisms that are very often encountered in different magazines, newspapers and televisions.

According to the students, only 40% of their teachers use standard Albanian language while teaching, more than 50% of them use a dialect form, and 10% of teachers mix the dialect and the standard language while teaching. Regarding the use of foreign words, students claim that most of their teachers (60%) rarely use any foreign English word, and 20% of them, according to the students, never use foreign words. But 20% of teachers use words with different origins during the teaching process. Some of the most frequent words used by teachers in the classroom are: *ok, yes, no, nothing important, don't worry be happy*, etc., most of which are English words. There are only few exceptions (*mercy, pozadina*).

Students claim that there are no foreign words in their books, or they are used very rarely, and when they encounter any foreign word, they usually understand it easily, and they sometimes ask their teachers for help. They also add that most of the foreign words they encounter at school are in their IT books, and at the same time, they identify internationalisms with English origin. The use of English words is understood as something common and their attitude towards them is very positive.

The 9th graders claim that they use English words in different occasions. The majority of them, 73%, use English words only with their friends, whereas 22% of the students claim to use

⁷ Shehu, H. (2009). *Çështje të gjuhës së folur të mjeteve të informimit masiv*. IIIrd International Seminar of Albanology – State University of Tetova, p.94.

English words even when they talk to their teachers. Only 5% of students use English foreign words with their family members.

English words that are very often used by them include: *bye, miss you, love you, hey, thanks, let's go, excellent, let's play, hello, please, yes, no, crazy, fine, good, how are you, what's up, Bluetooth, see, like, love, time is up, cool, oh my God, bro, sissy, man, how are you doing, goodbye, please, i-phone, what!, real, laptop* etc. Except these words, they also mentioned other English words such as: *ok, stress* and *weekend*, and they said that they use these forms even though there are words with the same meaning in Albanian language.

The use of anglicisms and foreign words with English origin by Albanian students should not be considered as a disturbing phenomenon as long as their use becomes necessary due to the lack of other alternatives or when there are lexical gaps in Albanian language. Using English words in cases when there is one or more corresponding forms of the certain word in Albanian language should be considered and prohibited. Teachers and educators are an important factor in raising the awareness of Albanian students in preserving Albanian language. Teachers need to use only the standard form of Albanian language during the teaching process. Foreign words can be used only in cases when their use is necessary to convey specific meanings and in cases when the lesson includes specific terminology. It is a well-known fact that students who attend classes with teachers who use standard Albanian language are obliged to speak pure Albanian in class as well. The same rule stands for anglicisms and foreign words. The less they are used by teachers, the less they will be used by students. In addition, it is recommended for teachers to improve students every time they use unnecessary foreign words. They should replace those words with Albanian words at the moment students use non-Albanian words. In this way, by trying to speak fluently and by only using Albanian words in front of their teachers, students will develop the habit of avoiding the use of unnecessary foreign language elements.

Conclusion

Albanian language is influenced by English language and English foreign words are now used in different discourses, especially by young students. They use them very often as part of their everyday communication. According to the questionnaire, Albanian students also use foreign words at school, especially when talking to the teachers whose foreign words themselves, and are not careful enough in maintaining the language.

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